

ENHANCING MATHEMATICS ACHIEVEMENT OF ACADEMICALLY GIFTED SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH DYSCALCULIA VIA ASSISTIVE TECHNOLOGY AND PEER TUTORING STRATEGY

FAGBEMI, Olusegun Olujide

Department of Special Education, University of Calabar, Calabar Nigeria

E-mail: segunjide30@gmail.com; Phone No: +234 703 014 5590

Orchid ID: 0000-0001-6809-4777

ALABI, Temitope

E-mail: alabitope32@hmail.com; Phone No: +234 806 566 6171

Orchid ID: 0009-0002-6398-1697

&

ODUMU, Bridget Omeno

Department of Special Education, University of Ibadan, Ibadan Nigeria

E-mail: bridggyy@yahoo.co.uk; Phone No: +234 803 638 0831

Orchid ID: 0009-0009-1321-7878

Abstract

This study investigated the effect of assistive technology and peer tutoring on mathematics achievement of academically gifted secondary school students with dyscalculia in Ibarapa Division of Oyo State, Nigeria. Three hypotheses guided the study. A Pretest-posttest quasi-experimental research design was used for this study. The study sample consisted of 178 academically gifted students with dyscalculia selected using a proportionate stratified sampling technique. They were grouped into two experimental groups and a control group. The three groups were pretested using the Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) designed by the researchers ($r = .78$). Treatment packages were administered to the experimental groups while the control group was not administered any treatment. Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics and analysis of covariance (ANCOVA). Ethical considerations were adhered to. Results show significant main effect of gender [$F(1, 176) = 19.336$; p -value = .000 < .05] on mathematics achievement of the participants and significant main effect of the treatment [$F(2, 175) = 464.770$; p -value = .000 < .05]. No significant interaction effect of gender and the treatment [$F(2, 175) = .050$; p -value = .824 < .05] was found. Investment in a variety of assistive technology designed to support students with dyscalculia and the establishment of peer tutoring programmes within the school was recommended.

Keywords: Assistive Technology; Academically Gifted; Dyscalculia; Mathematics Achievement; Secondary School Students; Peer Tutoring

Introduction

Dyscalculia is a specific learning disability that primarily affects a person's

ability to understand and manipulate numbers. Students with dyscalculia may have problems with basic arithmetic,

number sense, and or spatial reasoning. While dyscalculia can affect individuals of all intellectual abilities, its impact can be devastating for academically gifted students expected to excel in all subjects. Academically gifted students with dyscalculia often experience a significant discrepancy between their intellectual potential and mathematical achievement. This is a case comorbidity that can lead to frustration, confusion, a sense of inadequacy, loss of interest in schooling, absenteeism and complete drop-out of school if not tackled. They may feel overwhelmed by the complexity of mathematical concepts and struggle to keep up with their peers.

Academically gifted students with dyscalculia represent a unique population facing significant challenges in their academic pursuits. While they possess high intellectual abilities, their specific learning difficulties in mathematics can hinder their overall academic achievement and lead to frustration and discouragement. As noted by Fastame (2020), these students often possess high intelligence but struggle significantly with mathematical concepts, leading to frustration when their abilities do not align with their achievement in mathematics. One of the effects of dyscalculia on them is feelings of anger, anxiety, and low self-esteem which are exacerbated by their inability to grasp mathematical language and concepts (Anjum, Ansari & Ullah, 2023). These students may feel misunderstood or labelled as lazy, which can further alienate them from peers and educators (Nordman & Adcock, 2022).

To address the academic frustrations of academically gifted students with dyscalculia, it is essential to provide them with appropriate support and accommodations. This can be assistive technology such as calculators and digital manipulatives like blocks, counters and geometric shapes. These can support

individuals with dyscalculia to overcome their Mathematics challenges. Peers who excel in Mathematics can also be used to teach them for better outcomes than the traditional teacher instruction. The study is therefore borne out of the need to provide appropriate and beneficial intervention for classroom teachers dealing with academically gifted students with dyscalculia.

Academically Gifted Students

Academically gifted students, according to Burrell, Horsley and Moeed (2017) possess exceptional cognitive abilities, creativity, and leadership qualities that set them apart from their peers. Recognizing and nurturing these exceptional talents is crucial for the individual student's success and the nation's future development. These students, commonly referred to as high-ability students demonstrate exceptional intellectual or creative skills beyond their same-age peers. In Nigeria, these students are frequently referred to as gifted and talented learners. Adesina (2019) asserted that Nigerian schools do not have adequate resources to identify and support high-ability students. The study further noted that teachers are not adequately trained to recognize and support academically gifted learners in the classroom.

Key characteristics of high-ability students are rapid learning, strong memory, abstract and critical thinking, curiosity and intellectual drive (Jolly & Robins, 2016). They exhibit a strong thirst for knowledge and a desire to explore new ideas and concepts (Grieshaber & Kerr, 2018), creativity, imagination and innovation, fluency and flexibility, and sensitivity and emotional intelligence (Olatunde, 2020). Challenges faced by academically gifted students include underachievement in one or more subject areas where they may struggle. They also experience boredom as traditional

curriculum and instruction may not adequately challenge their abilities, leading to disengagement and underachievement (Owolabi, 2020).

Peer Tutoring Strategy

In peer tutoring, experienced students help less experienced ones learn by sharing their knowledge with the teacher's oversight. Peer tutoring is often preferred by educators as it increases the learning rate, contributes to social skill development, develops a range of other skills, and provides emotional benefits to the students (Dada, Ekim, Fagbemi, Mbakwe & Offiong, 2023). It is an instructional approach that involves pairing high-performing students with others while learning to achieve optimum benefits from each other, which helps significantly. As a result, peer tutoring enriches the learning experience for students, regardless of academic ability. (Muhammad, Abdullah & Osman, 2020). Muhammad, *et al.*, (2020) conceived peer tutoring as an operational strategy for involving learners and propping up academic achievement.

The advantages of peer tutoring over conventional strategies in enhancing academic achievement have been reported by several authors. The advantages are enhanced student interest, better academic achievement for the tutor and the tutee and better peer collaboration (e.g. Leung, 2019; Shin, Ok, Kang, & Bryant, 2019; Hickey & Flynn, 2019). Wolfe (2018) also noted that pairing high-performing students with others while learning to achieve optimum benefits from each other helps significantly. As a result, it enriches the student's educational experience irrespective of their academic ability.

Assistive Technology

Assistive technology is another intervention in this study. Assistive technology refers to a range of software and

hardware tools such as calculators, educational games, and interactive whiteboards that can help students with dyscalculia visualize mathematical concepts and improve their problem-solving skills (Rajkumar, 2018). When it comes to math, assistive technology can be incredibly helpful for students who struggle with certain concepts or processing information at a certain pace. Some examples of assistive technology for math include text-to-speech software, graphic organizers, and digital manipulatives which relate well to instruction in mensuration of plane shapes. These tools can help students with various learning styles and abilities to better understand and engage with math material, ultimately leading to improved confidence and success in the subject.

Theoretical Framework

This study is hinged on two major theories. They are the Universal Design for Learning (UDL) by Castro and Castro (2016) and Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory (1978). These two theories offer complementary frameworks for understanding and improving mathematics education for academically gifted secondary school students with dyscalculia. UDL emphasizes creating learning environments that are accessible and engaging for all students, while Vygotsky's theory highlights the importance of social interaction and cultural tools in cognitive development. UDL provides a set of principles to guide the design of instructional materials and activities that are inclusive and adaptable to diverse learner needs. By incorporating UDL principles, educators can create mathematics classrooms that are more accessible for students with dyscalculia. For example, providing multiple means of representation can help students with dyscalculia visualize mathematical concepts while offering multiple means of engagement can provide opportunities for

students to practice and apply their knowledge in meaningful ways.

Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory emphasizes the role of social interaction and cultural tools in learning. Peer tutoring can be seen as a form of social interaction that facilitates learning by providing students with opportunities to collaborate, communicate, and receive support from their peers. Additionally, assistive technology can be viewed as a cultural tool that can enhance learning by providing students with new ways to access and represent information. By combining UDL and Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory, educators can create mathematics classrooms that are both inclusive and supportive for students with dyscalculia. UDL principles can help to ensure that all students have equal access to learning opportunities, while Vygotsky's theory can guide the design of social and cultural supports that can enhance learning outcomes. By providing visual aids, alternate methods for understanding mathematical concepts, and assistance with calculations, assistive technology can help individuals with dyscalculia overcome their math challenges. The study is therefore borne out of the need to provide appropriate and beneficial intervention for classroom teachers dealing with academically gifted students with dyscalculia.

Statement of the Problem

Dyscalculia, a specific learning disability that impairs mathematical ability, poses significant challenges for many students. Despite the high intellectual potential of academically gifted students, those with dyscalculia are incapable of understanding fundamental mathematical concepts, leading to frustration, low self-esteem, and underachievement in mathematics. This is particularly problematic in secondary education, where the complexity of mathematical content increases rapidly. Moreover, a credit pass in

mathematics is one of the requirements for transition to higher education. This therefore means that dyscalculia can hinder academically gifted secondary school students from academic progression if not tackled.

Furthermore, traditional one-size-fits-all approaches to mathematics education fail to meet the unique needs of students with dyscalculia. This widens the gap between their potential and actual achievement, potentially limiting their future educational and career opportunities. Thus, there is an urgent need to develop effective interventions that can help gifted middle school students with dyscalculia overcome mathematical challenges and reach their full potential. The purpose of this study is to examine the effectiveness of assistive technology and peer tutoring as potential strategies to improve the mathematics achievement of these students.

Purpose of the Study

The major rationale for this study is to investigate the effect of assistive technology and peer tutoring on the mathematics ability of academically gifted secondary school students with dyscalculia in Ibarapa Division of Oyo State. Other objectives of the study are to:

1. Analyse the main effect of gender on mathematics achievement of academically gifted secondary school students with dyscalculia in Ibarapa Division of Oyo State.
2. Inquire into the main effect of treatments on mathematics achievement of academically gifted secondary school students with dyscalculia in Ibarapa Division of Oyo State.
3. Investigate the interaction effect of gender and treatments on mathematics achievement of academically gifted secondary school students with dyscalculia in Ibarapa Division of Oyo State.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at a .05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant effect of gender on mathematics achievement of academically gifted secondary school students with dyscalculia in Ibarapa Division of Oyo State.
2. There is no significant main effect of treatments on mathematics achievement of academically gifted secondary school students with dyscalculia in Ibarapa Division of Oyo State.
3. There is no significant interaction effect of gender and treatments on mathematics achievement of academically gifted secondary school students with dyscalculia in Ibarapa Division of Oyo State.

Methodology

Pretest-posttest quasi-experimental research design was used for this study. The target population for this study is all 2,745 academically gifted students with dyscalculia in public secondary schools in the Ibarapa Division of Oyo State. This figure was arrived after a preliminary investigation of the number of pupils with dyscalculia in the local governments concerned. Participants were Junior Secondary School students. Using the school record and teacher nomination, academically gifted students with dyscalculia were identified by teachers who taught the students. A proportionate stratified sampling technique was used to select 178 students for the study. This sample represents 6.4% of the total population. The study area is the Ibarapa Division of Oyo State which comprises three local government areas.

Ethical principles were strictly adhered to throughout the study. Informed consent was obtained from the schools, teachers and parents of concerned students

and their teachers as well. Confidentiality of participant data was ensured and data collected was securely stored. The participants were grouped into two experimental groups and a control group. The three groups were pretested using the Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) on Mensuration of Planes Shapes to assess their baseline. MAT was designed by the researchers and validated with the assistance of two experts in Measurement and Evaluation. 50 was the mark obtainable in the test. 10 students with exceptional mathematics ability were trained and used as facilitators for the study.

The treatment package was mathematics instruction in Mensuration of Plane Shapes for Experimental Group 1 using peer tutoring for 3 weeks and mathematics instruction in Mensuration of Plane Shapes for Experimental Group 2 using assistive technology mainly calculator and digital manipulatives such as blocks, counters, and geometric shapes for 3 weeks. The control group also had mathematics instruction in Mensuration of Plane Shapes using conventional method. The three groups were evaluated after the treatment.

Group 1:	R	O ₁	X	O ₂
Group 2:	R	O ₃	X	O ₄
Group 3:	R	O ₅	x	O ₆

Where:

01	Pre-test for experimental group 1
02	Post-test for experimental group 1
03	Pretest for experimental group 2
04	Posttest for control group
05	Pretest for control group
06	Post-test for control group
X	Treatment for the experimental group

Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics such as frequency count, percentage, mean and standard deviation while analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the hypotheses.

Table 1: Participants' Socio-Demographic Data

Variable	N	%	Mean	SD
Gender				
Male	87	49.4		
Female	91	50.6	1.56	
Total	178	100.0		2.02
Class				
JSS 1	55	30.9		
JSS 2	67	37.6	.501	
JSS 3	56	31.5		.802
Total	178	100.0		

Table 1 shows the participants' socio-demographic information. It shows that 178 students participated in the study. The male represents 49.4% while female participants represent 50.6% with a mean and standard deviation of 1.56 and 2.02 respectively showing a balance across

gender. The table also shows that participants in JSS 1 represent 30.9, those in JSS 2 represent 37.6% and those in JSS 3 represent 31.5% with a mean and standard deviation of .501 and .802 respectively showing even spread across the classes.

Table 2: Main Effects of Gender on Mathematics Achievement of Students with Dyscalculia in Mensuration of Plane Shapes

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: Treatments

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	4.405 ^a	1	4.405	19.336	.000	.099
Intercept	2178.023	1	2178.023	9560.607	.000	.982
Gender	4.405	1	4.405	19.336	.000	.099
Error	40.095	176	.228			
Total	2225.000	178				
Corrected Total	44.500	177				

a. R Squared = .099 (Adjusted R Squared = .094).

Table 2 shows the main effects of gender on mathematics achievement of students with dyscalculia is significant [$F(1, 176) = 19.336$; $p\text{-value} = .000 < .05$] with partial eta square .099 indicating a moderately significant effect of 9.9% effect on mathematics achievement of the

participants. Therefore, Hypothesis 1 is rejected as there is a significant main effect of gender on mathematics achievement of academically gifted secondary school students with dyscalculia in Ibarapa Division of Oyo State.

Table 3: Main Effects of Treatments on Mathematics Achievement of Students with Dyscalculia in Mensuration of Plane Shapes

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: Peer tutoring

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	17461.624 ^a	1	17461.624	464.770	.000	.725
Intercept	192326.972	1	192326.972	5119.098	.000	.967
Treatments	34923.248	2	34923.248	464.770	.000	.725
Error	6612.404	176	37.570			
Total	216401.000	178				
Corrected Total	24074.028	177				

a. R Squared = .725 (Adjusted R Squared = .724)

Table 3 shows the main effects of treatments on mathematics achievement of students with dyscalculia is significant [$F(2, 175) = 464.770$; $p\text{-value} = .000 < .05$] with partial eta square .725 indicating a high significant effect of 72.5% on mathematics achievement of the

participants. Therefore, Hypothesis 2 is rejected as there is significant main effect of treatments on mathematics achievement of academically gifted secondary school students with dyscalculia in Ibarapa Division of Oyo State.

Table 4: Interaction Effects of Gender and Treatments on Mathematics Achievement of Students with Dyscalculia in Mensuration of Plane Shapes

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: Peer tutoring

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p-value	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	17610.203 ^a	3	5870.068	158.017	.000	.732
Intercept	173013.059	1	173013.059	4657.346	.000	.964
Treatment	16695.743	1	16695.743	449.433	.000	.721
Gender	146.462	1	146.462	3.943	.049	.022
Treatment * Gender	1.850	1	1.850	.050	.824	.000
Error	6463.825	174	37.148			
Total	216401.000	178				
Corrected Total	24074.028	177				

a. R Squared = .732 (Adjusted R Squared = .727)

Table 4 shows the main effects of treatments on the mathematics achievement of students with dyscalculia is significant [$F(2, 175) = .050$; $p\text{-value} = .824 > .05$] with partial eta square .000 indicating no significant effect on mathematics

achievement of the participants. Therefore, Hypothesis 3 is accepted as there is no significant effects of gender and treatments on mathematics achievement of academically gifted secondary school

students with dyscalculia in Ibarapa Division of Oyo State.

Discussion of Results

The researchers investigated the impact of assistive technology and peer tutoring on the mathematics achievement of academically gifted secondary school students with dyscalculia in Ibarapa Division of Oyo State. Hypothesis 1 states that there is no significant main effect of gender on mathematics achievement of academically gifted secondary school students with dyscalculia in Ibarapa Division of Oyo State. However, it was found that gender has a significant main effect on mathematics achievement of academically gifted secondary school students with dyscalculia in Ibarapa Division of Oyo State. The findings of this study align with previous research that has consistently shown gender disparities in mathematics achievement. For example, Räsänen et al (2021) found that girls outperform boys in standardized mathematics assessments. This gender gap persists even among academically gifted students with dyscalculia, as evidenced by Wang and Degol (2017). Several factors may contribute to this gender difference, including societal stereotypes, differential teaching practices, and variations in cognitive abilities.

However, these conclusions might not be valid in all situations. While gender may be a significant predictor of mathematics achievement in certain contexts, individual differences and cultural factors can also influence outcomes. In addition, the specific interventions employed in this study, such as assistive technology and peer tutoring, may have moderated the effects of gender on mathematics achievement. Furthermore, the study's findings highlight the importance of addressing gender-specific challenges in mathematics education. By implementing targeted interventions and

creating inclusive learning environments, educators can help to close the gender gap and ensure that all students, regardless of their gender, have equal opportunities to succeed in mathematics.

Hypothesis 2 states that there is no significant main effect of treatment on mathematics achievement of academically gifted secondary school students with dyscalculia in Ibarapa Division of Oyo State. It was however found that the treatment (peer tutoring and assistive technology) has a significant main effect on mathematics achievement of academically gifted secondary school students with dyscalculia in Ibarapa Division of Oyo State. The study's findings align with previous research that has demonstrated the effectiveness of assistive technology and peer tutoring in improving mathematics achievement among students with dyscalculia. For instance, Rajkumar (2018) found that engagement with specialized software, such as equation editors and calculators, can significantly enhance the mathematical skills of students with dyscalculia.

Similarly, Leung (2019), Shin, Ok, Kang, & Bryant (2019) as well as Hickey and Flynn, (2019) reported that peer tutoring, in which students with dyscalculia receive individualized support from their peers, can lead to substantial gains in mathematics achievement while Dada *et al.*, (2023) and Adeneye and Awofala (2024) also found that peer tutoring strategy enhanced secondary school students achievement in Mathematics and Muhammad et al. (2020) noted that peer tutoring enhances the learning of Mathematics irrespective of the student's ability. Therefore, the combined effects of assistive technology and peer tutoring may be particularly beneficial for academically gifted secondary school students with

dyscalculia. By providing students with the tools and support they need to overcome their mathematical challenges, these interventions can help them to unlock their full potential and achieve academic success.

Hypothesis 3 states that there is no significant interaction effect of gender and treatment on mathematics achievement of academically gifted secondary school students with dyscalculia in Ibarapa Division of Oyo State. The finding confirms the hypothesis. The study's findings suggest that while gender and the interventions (peer tutoring and assistive technology) have significant main effects on mathematics achievement, there is no significant interaction between these factors. This indicates that the effectiveness of the interventions is not dependent on the gender of the students. In other words, both boys and girls with dyscalculia benefit equally from these interventions. This finding is consistent with previous studies that have shown that gender does not moderate the effects of educational interventions on mathematics achievement. For example, Mamman, Dahiru and Hamma (2023) found that both boys and girls with dyscalculia showed similar improvements in mathematical skills when provided with specialized instruction. Similarly, Yusha'u (2013) had earlier reported that peer tutoring was equally effective for male and female students with dyscalculia.

Recommendations

Given the findings of this study, the following recommendations were necessary:

1. Secondary schools should invest in and provide access to different assistive technology tools specifically designed to support students with dyscalculia. These tools can include calculators, equation editors, graph paper, and

software that can help with number recognition and manipulation.

2. Secondary schools should establish peer tutoring programmes within schools where students with dyscalculia can receive individualized support from their peers. This can help to foster a supportive learning environment and improve students' confidence and motivation.

Conclusion

The study investigated the impact of assistive technology and peer tutoring on the mathematics achievement of academically gifted secondary school students with dyscalculia in Ibarapa Division of Oyo State. The findings revealed that both interventions had a significant positive effect on students' mathematical achievement. Furthermore, the study found no significant interaction between gender and the treatments, suggesting that both boys and girls with dyscalculia benefited equally from these interventions. These results align with previous research that has demonstrated the effectiveness of assistive technology and peer tutoring in improving mathematics outcomes for students with dyscalculia. The findings also highlight the importance of providing targeted support to students with dyscalculia, regardless of their gender, to help them achieve their full potential in mathematics.

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